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MADAD-I-MA'ASH GRANTS UNDER THE MUGHULS

By

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(I have purposely used the term *madad-i-ma'ash* and not the term *siyār ḡhāl* under which Abū al-Faḍl in his *Ā'in i Akbari* describes the subject. The term used commonly during the times of Akbar and his successors, both in official and non-official documents, was *madad-i-ma'ash* and very rarely *siyār ḡhāl*. The original term *madad-i-ma'ash* was retained for official purposes, firstly, as it was well known in India and secondly, in order to distinguish it from *siyār ḡhāls* in Muslim lands outside India during the sixteenth century. There the term *siyār ḡhāl* denoted a military grant for which in India the terms *jāgir* and *iqṭāh* were commonly used, and also as a maintenance grant for certain categories of Muslims corresponding to the *madad-i-ma'ash* grant—grant which entailed no obligation to maintain a contingent or render any active service in return for this favour.)¹

State support to certain persons, particularly to men of learning and piety, has been a common feature of all state-systems throughout the ages. In Islamic countries this practice stems from the recognition of the claim to state-aid by Muslim governments in case of such members of the community as were not able to support themselves.²

*This paper was read at the Tenth Session of the Pakistan History Conference held at Rajshahi in 1960.

¹ The present writer has discussed the nature of *siyār ḡl āl* lands under the Mughuls in a paper contributed to the Commemoration Volume presented to the late Sir Jadunath Sarkar and published by the Punjab University Hoshiarpore (India). This paper embodies the information derived from a study of documents relating to *madad-i-ma'ash* grants in the Record Office at Allahabad. The present writer has already edited two volumes of such documents which have been published by the Allahabad Record Office, Allahabad, India.

² For the categories of persons who were generally granted *madad-i-ma'ash*, see Abū al-Faḍl, *Ā'in i Akbari*, Vol. I, page 273.

In medieval times this claim was recognized and regulated by the state both by the Sultans of Delhi and the Mughul rulers. Such financial assistance was given either in the form of grant of rent-free lands or assignation of revenue from land or sometimes as a charge on the octroi duties from specified areas or a cash grant in the form of *wazifah* or *rozinah*, i.e. daily allowance. This practice has left a permanent imprint not only on agrarian relationship in India but on the character and economic development of the social group from which came the recipients of such grants. In this paper I have briefly discussed the grants commonly known as *madad-i-ma'ash* and the social and economic implications of the same.

Procedure :

The *Şadr-al-Şadr* was the officer responsible for the administration of the *madad-i-ma'ash* grants but the rulers vigilantly supervised the work of the *Şadr* and jealously guarded the abuse of this power by the *Şadr's* department. The *Şadr* was assisted by the *Bitikchi*, the *Qāđi* and the *Mir 'Adl*. Every important paper dealing with such grants bore the *Şadr's* seal. The power of the *Şadr* to grant *madad-i-ma'ash* was severely curtailed by Akbar and gradually reduced to the grant of fifteen bighas of land and later even this authority was taken away from him.¹ When Musawi Khan in the time of Shah Jahān exceeded his authority he was removed from office.² The *Şadr*, however, continued to recommend such grants and authorize verification, confirmation and renewal of old grants. In the provinces the provincial *Şadr* exercised this power³ and in the parganahs the *mutawallis* appointed by a royal order supervised the administration of such lands.⁴

¹ For Akbar's regulations in regard to these grants and the curtailment of the powers of the *Şadrs*, see Blochman's note in '*Āini Akbari*, English translation, Vol. I, page 280-85 and my article in J. N. Sarkar Commemoration volume.

² Ibn-i-Hasan, *Central Structure of the Mughal Empire*, page 275: Lahore, *Badshah Nama*, II, pp. 365, 366.

³ *Mirat-i-Ahamdi*, Supplement, p. 173.

⁴ *Dasitir-ul-Amal-i-Bekas*, manuscript in Aligarh Muslim University Library.

The following procedure was followed in granting such lands.¹ In the first instance a report was submitted to the imperial office that such and such persons deserved *madad-i-ma'ash*.² The report, as soon as it was received, was recorded in the *siāha*³ (the daily court diary) and then presented to the emperor. The emperor, if he approved of it, issued verbal orders for such an assignment. The details of the grant and the name of the *Şadr* were recorded in the *yaddāsh-t-wāqi'ah* (official record) by *wāq'iah-i-nigār*. The *Şadr* then ordered that the *yaddāsh-t* (report) or memo. should be presented to the emperor again. This was known as '*arḍ-i-muqarrar*. When this had been presented for the second time, the *Şadr* issued instructions that a *farmān* should be prepared within the period specified by him. It was only then that the actual *farmān* was prepared. It contained the details of the land so granted, the name of the grantee, and the instructions to the officers concerned to comply with the order and make over the possession of the land so assigned to the grantee. The *ziman* (abstract), giving the procedure of the grant as stated above and entered in the *yaddāsh-t-wāqi'ah* was recorded on the back of the *farmān*.

In accordance with the terms of the *farmān*, a *parwānah* was issued by the *Şadr*. It also contained a *ziman* by the *Şadr* which was a summary of the order. The *parwānah* contained the date of the issue of the *farmān*, specification of the assignment and the name of the assignee and directed the officers concerned to carry out the order.⁴

¹ Most of the information contained in this section is based on a study of Allahabad Record Office Documents, and *Farhang-i-Kardani*.

² *Farhang-i-Kardani*, p. 39 (author's manuscript).

³ Register recording proceeding and transactions of the court; a day-to-day diary called also "*Siyaha Huḍūr*."

⁴ A well preserved *farmān* of Awrangazib issued in the third year of his reign in the possession of a zamindār family of Sambhal (U. P., India) closely follows the details given here.

Nature of the Grant :

Unlike the *jāgir* a *madad-i-ma'ash* grant was not contingent on the performance of any civil or military duties.¹ It carried with it no such obligation except that the recipient was expected to be loyal to the dynasty and pray for its perpetual existence and stability. The motives, however, of these rulers in granting such lands were not always disinterested. One is reminded of the remarks of Justinian in whose time there was considerable increase in the number of monasteries and the perquisites of the monks. "If they (the monks)," Justinian remarks, "with their hands pure and souls bare, offer to God prayers for the State, it is evident that it will be well with army, and the cities will prosper, and our land will bear fruits and the sea will yield us its products, for their prayers will propitiate God's favour towards the whole State." Thus it was an act of favour and a mark of good will on the part of the sovereign in his relationship to a particular person or a group of persons. As such these grants resembled ecclesiastical grants so common in western Europe.

Such a grant was in the nature of transference by the state of the right of collection of revenue and other cesses to the grantee. The state, however, reserved the right to cancel, resume, decrease, or extend the original grant.² The land so granted was hereditary in character and immune from state dues as well as administrative interference. Sometimes the government insisted on occasionally examining the validity of the grant and renewing the same with any modification desired by it. In certain cases the grantee was exempted expressly from the necessity of periodic renewal of the grant. Not only were such lands immune from the payment of land revenue, they were expressly freed from the payment of the various cesses and dues to which other categories of land were subject.³ These lands could

¹ Though it was a benefaction independent of the obligation to perform any functions, the recipients were sometime required to perform civil duties. Budānī who had a *siyār-i-hāl* of 1,000 bighas was required to be in attendance at the court and when he left the court the size of the grant was reduced.

² *A'in*, I, pp. 140, 141.

³ The cesses which were expressly remitted varied from *farmān* to *farmān*. The usual term used was *awāridāt-i-sultānī* and "*taulif-i-diwānī*." These *farmāns* throw an interesting side light on the heavy cesses which were levied from the peasants. The most common cesses were *qunlig'iah*, *pish-kash*, *jaribansh*, *dih'tānah*, *muhas-silanah*, *dārughānah*, *bigār*, *shikār*, *dih-nimi*, *muqaddamī*, *jaḡirdārī*, *dui*, *dabi-i-har salah*, etc.

be bequeathed but not sold or given away as a gift. In a reported case where the legal heirs of a deceased grantee filed a suit for the recovery of the *madad-i-ma'āsh* land which their father had alienated, the *Qādi* who tried the case gave the ruling that the deceased could not legally alienate the land and ordered the restoration of the land to the legal heirs.¹ Against this we have the evidence of two documents recording the sale of such lands during the post-Aurangzib period.² Similarly though immunity from land revenue was the essence of a *madad-i-ma'āsh* grant we have again documents of the period referring to the assessment of such lands though the rate of assessment appears to have been much lower than in the case of other lands subject to *ḍabt*.³

The *madad-i-ma'āsh* land could be granted out of *Khālsah lands*⁴ *jāgīr lands*⁵ or dead lands.⁶ Generally one-half of the grant consisted of waste or uncultivated land and the other half of land which was already under cultivation.⁷ Efforts were made in the time of Akbar to separate the *madad-i-ma'āsh* lands from the *jāgīr* lands and to consolidate such holdings by proper demarcation but such lands sometimes got mixed up with *jāgīr* lands in which case instructions were issued that such lands were to be excluded from the annual *ḍabt* (measurement and assessment) and no *jāgīrdārī* or *karorī* dues were to be levied.

Various attempts were made from the time of Akbar onwards to fix the ceiling as to the size of such grants but with little success. An examination of the *farmāns* granting such lands shows that the size of a grant varied from 15 bighas to 4,000 bighas. Large-size grants were, however, very rare and the weaker a ruler the larger was the size of the grant.⁸

¹ Allahabad documents.

² Allahabad Documents Nos. 1, 218.

³ *Ibid.*, Nos. 294, 296.

⁴ *Dastūr-al-'Amal-i-Bakes*, 40 a.b.

⁵ Allahabad Documents, 3, 156, 159, 162.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 156, 157, 159, 160, 162.

⁷ *A'in*, I, p. 141. That there were some exceptions to this practice is evident from a study of some documents. See Akbar's *Farmān* dated 986 A. H. and Jahāngīr's *Farmān* dated 1004 A. H., Allahabad Documents.

⁸ Allahabad Documents—Documents No. 154, dated 12th R. Y. of Shah Jahān—400 bighas, No. 144, 1562 bighas, No. 180, 3039 bighas, No. 199, 2,220 bighas.

Lands granted to non-Muslims or in favour of their religious and charitable institutions were rarely designated as *madad-i-ma'ash* grants. The grant of a *madad-i-ma'ash* to the Parsis and the Jesuit Fathers are rare instances of grants being so described. The grants made in favour of non-Muslims were generally designated as *in'am* lands and carried the same immunities as the *madad-i-ma'ash* lands. The recipients of *madad-i-ma'ash* grants included poets, *shaikhs*, *sufis*, *qadis*, *muezzins*, *mutawallis*, orphans, widows, *saiyyads* and even musicians. A village elder with whom Akbar had stayed for a night was given *madad-i-ma'ash*.¹

Verification, Confirmation and Renewal of Grants:

All *madad-i-ma'ash* grants were subject to periodic verification and confirmation by the *ṣadr* in order to check fraudulent practices on the part of the grantees who very often in collusion with government officials were guilty of such practices. Sometimes a grant was specially exempted from renewal. The grantees were required to appear before the *Ṣadr* for verification (*taṣḥīḥ*) of their claims and produce evidence to the land being in their actual possession, that they had no other means of livelihood and that the former *ṣadrs* had duly verified and confirmed the grant.

Succession to Madad-i-Ma'ash Grants :

Elaborate rules governing succession to such lands were made and promulgated from time to time. The following summary of the two rare documents pertaining to the reign of Awrangzib are of interest as describing in detail such rules.² Important cases involving disputes as to succession, were decided not by the *qadis* but by the emperor. The two most important cases recorded are those relating to the cases of the rival claimants of the *dargāhs* at Ajmir and Uch.³

Document No. 1 :

Parwana issued by Jumaat-ul Mulk Raja Raghunath, dated 9 Jamādi al-Awwal, 1071 Third R.Y. of Awrangzib

Regulations concerning those who are in enjoyment of *madad-i-ma'ash*: where an original grantee has died and has left as his heir

¹ Nizām al-Dīn, *Ṭabaqāt-i-Akbari*, vol. II, p. 336.

² My attention to these documents was drawn by my former pupil and colleague, Dr. Irfān Habib, who was good enough to have personally copied them for me.

³ The hereditary right of the grantee to hold their lands was recognized by Lord Cornwallis—Lawrence's suggestion that all such lands should be resumed was turned down by the Punjab Government, not out of respect for their legal claims but because of the political exigency.

a son or a daughter, or the sons of the latter, his *madad-i-ma'ash* land if equal to 30 bighas or less than that was to be confirmed in the name of his heir. In case the area of such grant was more than 30 bighas, half of it was to be left with the heir and the other half was to be resumed. In case the heirs were not satisfied with the reduced grant they could make a representation before the Emperor and establish their claim to a larger grant.

Further, it was ordered that where a person was in enjoyment of *madad-i-ma'ash* or *wazifah* or *rozinah* and there was no suspicion about the genuineness of the *farmān* granting the land, such grant was to be confirmed. In the case of the death of the recipient of a grant of the *farmān* contained provision for the continuance of the grant in favour of a son, enquiries should be made about him and of his son and half of the said grant should be continued in his name. In case of there being no son or grandson as legal heir the grant should be resumed. A daily allowance of the value of less than half of the income from such grant should be provided for his heirs and the grant or *wazifah* resumed.

(Reference is here made to an earlier *farmān* dated 7th *Rabi' al-Thani*, 1069 and its violation by the *Şadrs* who have allowed the heirs to enjoy the whole of the grant or more than half.) Further, the present *şadrs* have resumed in some cases the grants with retrospective effect with the result that sons of the grantees being unable to meet the demand of arrears have fled their lands and some have died. It is now ordered that in case of persons who were in enjoyment of grants before the Emperor's accession and had valid *farmāns*, no interference should be made with them. Those who had died after the coronation or who die subsequently, in their case if the grant amounted to 20 bighas or more, one half of it was to be resumed and the other half was to be confirmed on the original grantee.

Document No. 2 :

Farmān dated 15th Rabi' al-Awwal, 34 R.Y.

This *farmān* is addressed to the *Umara*, the *Qādis*, *Şadrs* and *Mutşaaddis*.

God having given the kings sovereignty over the kingdom. He has entrusted the maintenance of the poor and the indigent to kings.

Therefore, in accordance with the practice of the early rulers the maintenance of the *aima*, both females and males, according to their desserts, is incumbent on kings.

All grants already made should be continued without any change or diminution in the names of the heirs of the deceased and in case of such heirs who hold already other grants the share in those grants should be acknowledged and that should be considered as an additional grant. In case of dispute amongst the heirs, the rules laid down in the *farmān* should be carried out.

In case the deceased had assigned the land to his grandson, the grandson should be allowed to retain the share enjoyed by his father during the latter's lifetime.

Where a grantee leaves a son and a daughter and the daughter is married or she has received land from her husband, the entire property of the deceased should go to the son, and the daughter was to have no share in it as provision for her livelihood had already been made. If the daughter of the deceased is a widow and has no other means of livelihood or if there are other women, as claimants to the land, maintenance for them is to be provided out of the daughter's share. In case of the daughter being the sole heir the entire land is to go to her.

If a grantee leaves a widow, the land is to be granted to her and in case of her death, it is to go to the heirs of her husband. If there are no heirs of the husband, the land is to go to the heirs of the widow after her death. In case of deceased leaving a mother or a grandmother, the land is to be divided amongst them. If the deceased leaves a nephew or a sister's son, the property is to be distributed amongst them according to their needs. In case of there being no heirs the property is to be resumed. Such grants are to be immune from State dues, executive and revenue, and from *jāgīr* and *karori* cesses.

Jāgīr and Madad-i-Ma'āsh grants:

Whereas in the case of *Jāgīr* the emperor could at any time resume it or reduce it or transfer it the *madad-i-ma'āsh* grant were more

stable and all that Akbar did was to "curtail the economic basis" of the financial independence of the religious classes by his administrative regulations in order to permit a more uniform application of his agrarian measures. Whereas a *jāgīr* carried with it an obligation to render service, the owner of a *madad-i-ma'āsh* grant had ordinarily no such obligation. The *jāgīr* was not hereditary grant and conveyed no proprietary right on land. It was, therefore, described in terms of income from it. As against it *madad-i-ma'āsh* grant was hereditary and passed from father to son and was described in terms of its size. The *jāgīr* was a very large possession while a *madad-i-ma'āsh* grant was a small one. The *jāgīrdārs* did not usually live in their *jāgīrs* while the owners of *madad-i-ma'āsh* lands usually, if not always, lived on their holdings and were expected to sink wells, layout orchards and build *chaupāls* there. Their connection with their holdings was more personal and intimate.

It is difficult to determine the value of the *madad-i-ma'āsh* lands in terms of revenue. That they constituted a substantial portion of the state revenues is patent from the data available in the *Āin*. The revenue from these grants amounted to more than 3 per cent of the revenue of the whole and in certain reigns to as much as 19 per cent. Considering how heavily the peasantry was taxed and the vexatious cesses they had to pay, the grantees of *madad-i-ma'āsh* were financially in a sounder position as there were in most cases no demands on their time or labour.

General Observations :

The *madad-i-ma'āsh* grants though fulfilling a great social need and providing charitable assistance to the needy and the deserving middle class, immobilized much of the wealth of the empire and deprived its limited Muslim manpower of more creative and useful pursuits. Abul Faḍl speaks of the grantees of *madad-i-ma'āsh* as "an army of prayer," and remarks that though there is no country in which there would not be any of them (that is worthy and needy persons), however, in Hindustan there are more of them than anywhere else". When Akbar proceeded to regularize these grants and drastically cut down their size there was much resentment amongst the grantees. This elicited from Budāunī the remark that as a result of Akbar's measures "in the cities respect for the families of *Shaikhs*

and the *a'imah* and for famous and illustrious people vanished "and that because the *Pādshāh* interferred in the management of *madad-i-ma'ash* land" God interferred in the management of his domains".

As I have remarked earlier these grants were as much motivated by philanthropic considerations as they were by imperial needs. Akbar, though he did all he could to curb the power of the Muslim religious classes, was all the time careful of the claims of the Muslim middle class. Religion for Akbar was both a source of strength as well as of weakness. It was the only bond of union which kept the Muslim populace together and it at the same time was a constant irritant to the non-Muslim subjects of the empire corroding the bonds which held them together. These grantees scattered throughout the empire and with interests and contacts linked with the rural areas were useful as means for the promotion of communal harmony and understanding. The regularisation and control of *madad-i-ma'ash* grants further was an instrument of long range sound economic policy. In the first instance it was a step towards the creation of small class of landed proprietors which tended to limit the expansion and activities of landed aristocracy. It became clear that the dispenser of economic freedom and social prestige was the Emperor. By making the middle and lower strats of society dependent on the state he limited the position of the high status aristocratic group and controlled their vertical mobility. He could not resist the claims of special interest groups on account of fear of social unrest but he maintained a tight hold over them as this status group, potentially active and culturally creative, could be used as the channel of communication between the different sections of society. But these controls prevented rather than encourage the creation of an economically active group. The overvaluation of landed property as a symbol and a means of power, prestige, and economic security weakened the interest of this class in other economic activities as this social group was too proud to take to trade or craftsmanship and too lazy to adopt the active profession of arms which was then the only passport to social distinction or economic freedom. Lord Hastings thus characterised these grants: "Their owners at the present time" says he... "are obliged for this either to prejudices or to false charity, or to the misdirected favour of the heads of previous governments and other persons in power." It

was this social group which was hard hit by the fall of the Mughal empire, and constituted now not "an army of prayers" but an army of the unemployed constantly discontented and disillusioned. They are like the drones in the social beehive and it would be an interesting subject to study the role of this group in the development of Muslim society during the post-Mutiny period. Whatever may be said against this group they were the real repositories of Muslim ethical and cultural traditions and though financially weak were loyal to their religion and culture.

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